

Milestone report MS7

Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project is supported by four driver projects (hereafter Drivers), i.e. use cases which are prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities:

- Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision (EMBL, CRG, BSC)
- Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data (CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI)
- Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe (ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN)
- Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data (Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2)

The Drivers (united in WP7) first of all inform the development of and validate the blueprint and secondly provide user input to the provider forum by stating their requirements for a TRE.

This report summarises the groundwork laid to arrive at a harmonised set of requirements from the four Drivers, taking the perspective of end users. It is based on the outcomes of five workshops: a generic one across the four Drivers (June 17th, 2024) and four focused ones over July/August 2024, one organised by each of the Drivers. While the ultimate goal for WP7 would be to arrive at a comprehensive initial set of requirements gathered between the four Drivers, these first workshops focused on more basic questions like:

- What is a TRE from the perspective of the Drivers?
- Why has the Driver elected to use a TRE?
- What would be the user journey through the TRE?

The present milestone report summarises the current status as a result of the workshops. It concludes with a series of next steps to get more clarity on the open aspects that need to be filled before the end of the first year in order to arrive at a comprehensive set of requirements from the four Drivers.

How will this Milestone contribute to the overall project objectives?

- The Architecture WP will match the outputs of this milestone against the blueprint federated architecture, to identify gaps in existing 1) architectural specifications 2) data requirements 3) legal requirements and agreements 4) operational procedures.
- The user journeys identified in this milestone are crucial for identifying gaps in existing TRE providers.

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- The current milestone is the initial step for building a requirement gathering framework for anyone who considers building a TRE.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

The M7.1 milestone report on drivers baseline requirements has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No. and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP4, WP5)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP2, WP3)	Yes
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP2) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP2, WP5)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP6)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP6)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP4, WP5).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP4)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP5)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP4).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures	No

<p>framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP5)</p> <p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP4, WP5).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP4, WP5).</p> <p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP2, WP4) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP3).</p> <p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1, WP2).</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1, WP2).</p> <p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP2).</p> <p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP4).</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p> <p>No</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP3)	Yes
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3. Methods

This EOSC-ENTRUST milestone report summarises the baseline requirements gathered from the Drivers. These requirements serve as input for the project’s providers forum (WP10) and the TRE Blueprint (WP13).

To lay the groundwork for a common framework for gathering requirements and to identify gaps and overlaps among the drivers, a design thinking approach has been employed, with specific steps followed for each Driver (as illustrated in Figure 1). The SATRE² (*Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments*) framework, widely recognised in the UK, has served as a key reference in this process. This framework defines the capabilities expected from a TRE, categorised into mandatory and optional requirements. We used this framework as a foundation in our design thinking approach to develop the initial set of requirements:

- Determine the core problem the driver aims to solve
- Define the users
- Define the user journey (for this, an example user journey was provided, see Figure 2)
- Determine which capabilities from the SATRE framework are most important to the driver
- Gather requirements based on the users and user journey, using SATRE as a framework
- Identify gaps and next steps

Figure 1: Process followed to gather requirements from the four Drivers

The four Drivers differ significantly in the current baseline situation: some already have an existing collaboration between Driver partners while others still have to initiate their collaboration. Likewise, some have a mature TRE while others do not (yet) use one. Therefore, Drivers were also asked to report their current status with regard to TREs and identify: 1) what still needs to be determined, and, 2) which questions still need to be answered before the Driver can deliver a first comprehensive list of requirements.

Information about the Drivers and their requirements was gathered in a series of online workshops: 1) a common workshop for all Drivers to create common ground and define the scope and framework for requirements gathering, and, 2) a series of four workshops for each individual Driver to gather more information on the Driver’s need for a TRE and to gather initial requirements. Requirements were gathered in a common requirements matrix

² <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

(.csv published with this report), where the Drivers suggested requirements and also determined for both their own requirements and those suggested by other Drivers whether each requirement is a *Must have*, *Should have*, *Could have*, or *Won't have* for the Driver (through the MoSCoW method³). Moreover, each requirement was mapped to the SATRE framework. For further details on the information included in the requirements matrix, please refer to the “Readme” sheet.

Figure 2: Example user journey provided to the Drivers. DAC: Data Access Committee, SPE: Secure Processing Environment

³ The term MoSCoW is an acronym derived from the first letter of each of four prioritisation categories: *M* - *Must have*, *S* - *Should have*, *C* - *Could have*, *W* - *Won't have*.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision

4.1.1 Aim and scope

Driver 1 tackles the secure management and cross-border sharing of sensitive genomic data, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). TREs provide a controlled environment for secondary use of genomic data, overcoming challenges related to data protection and legal restrictions.

Key problems addressed:

- **Secure Data Access:** Enabling researchers to access and analyse genomic data while adhering to strict privacy regulations by means of a common identity and authorisation infrastructure.
- **Uniform Data Management:** By offering established governance criteria and centralised data management to data controllers, TREs promote data submissions and sharing.
- **Cross-border Data Sharing:** Facilitating the integration and analysis of data from multiple jurisdictions.
- **Resource Optimisation:** Utilising TREs to reduce data transfer and storage costs, and provide scalable computational resources.

4.1.2 Users and user journey

Involved partners:

- **Researchers:** The primary end users who seek access to and analyse genomic data for scientific research.
- **Data Submitters:** Responsible for the secure management, submission, and ongoing protection of the data within the TRE.
- **Infrastructure Providers:** Ensure that the TRE infrastructure meets the technical requirements for secure data storage, access, and analysis.
- **Regulatory Bodies:** Oversee and ensure compliance with data protection regulations and ethical guidelines.

User Journey:

Figure 3: Visual representation of user journey for Driver 1

High-level description of user journey as illustrated in Figure 3:

- **Data Discovery:** Researchers identify and locate relevant genomic datasets within the TRE network.
- **Access Application:** Researchers submit requests to access the data, which are reviewed and approved by Data Custodians, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards by signing a Data Access Agreement (DAA).
- **Data Access and Analysis:** Once approved, researchers securely access and analyse the data within the TRE, supported by the necessary infrastructure (i.e., secure processing environment, software installation, data storage, etc.).
- **Compliance and Reporting:** After analysis, researchers ensure their findings adhere to regulatory and ethical standards, with oversight from Regulatory Bodies.

4.1.3 Status

Driver 1 partners are engaged with TREs at different stages:

- **CSC:** Operates SD Services for secure data processing⁴, which are in active use exclusively for academic research purposes. Specifically, SD Desktop enables managing and analysing sensitive data. It also supports the use case of restricted access to secondary use of health data. Additionally, CSC maintains three proprietary secure data processing environments for national government organisations.
- **BSC/CRG:** In the process of developing a TRE to process, among others, genomic data coming from local and trustful data archives like EGA (European Genome-Phenome Archive) or the Spanish federated EGA node - still in planning

⁴ <https://research.csc.fi/sensitive-data-services-for-research>

stages. Legal agreements, such as those with EGA, will need to be reviewed to ensure the alignment with the new data processing model.

4.1.4 Key capabilities

SATRE framework capabilities important for the driver:

- Governance Requirements
- Internal auditing
- End user computing
- Information security
- Infrastructure Management
- Data Lifecycle Management
- Identity and Access Management
- Security Levels and Tiering
- Legal Services
- Business Continuity Management

Key capabilities missing from the SATRE framework:

- **Anonymisation:** Guidelines for anonymisation techniques to protect patient privacy across all participating institutions
- **Internet Connection from Within the TRE:** Allow for secure internet connectivity within TREs to access external resources necessary for genomic analysis, such as reference genomes and annotation databases.
- **Scalable Infrastructure:** To manage large-scale genomic datasets efficiently.

4.1.5 Uncertainties and next steps

For Driver 1, uncertainties lie in the following factors:

- Secondary use law in Finland is currently being updated with an expectation of the first solution to be ready by the end of the year. The update aims to somewhat relax the requirements to allow for broader use of data under the secondary law in Finland.
- Legal basis is still changing (EHDS) and this means it is currently difficult to set some requirements in the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)⁵.
- Depending on specific node implementations, another point of uncertainty would be the possibility - or impossibility - of allowing internet connection from within an SPE making online public research databases accessible.

As a next step, Driver 1 has identified:

- Survey design to gather specific data holder's requirements, afterwards to be mapped to the SATRE framework

⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

4.2 Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data

4.2.1 Aim and scope

Driver 2 establishes a set of definitions to ease the sharing of controlled/secure access data across countries. The scope of the driver is to create a framework to mitigate cross-national disparities that may prevent data sharing. Disparities may exist in many forms:

- incompatible legislation around data sharing and governance;
- different arrangements may exist for licensing or access conditions for data use;
- a lack of technical interoperability between platforms;
- different data management standards and formats.

Where two or more countries wish to share data, a TRE recognised as a safe data-sharing environment by all countries concerned can help to achieve this. The driver partners, UKDS, GESIS and TARKI, co-ordinated by CESSDA, are working together to advance and ease cross-national data sharing.

The UK Data Service (UKDS) and GESIS-Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (GESIS) can contribute to the creation of the framework to mitigate cross-national disparities. Both organisations have mature TREs and are experienced in negotiating across countries to enable data sharing. They have collaborated successfully to resolve legislative, data access, licensing, technical and data management issues. They are members of the International Data Access Network (IDAN),⁶ founded in 2018 and were partners in the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project⁷, specifically Work Package (WP) 5.4. Remote Access to Sensitive Data (2019-2022).

TARKI, the Hungarian National Social Science Data Archive, aims to share data internationally, but faces challenges. It faces several key issues:

- **Rising Demand:** With increasing use of sensitive data, Hungarian researchers are turning to TARKI for guidance. TARKI needs to enhance its preparedness.
- **Data Linkage:** TARKI has some expertise in linking anonymised surveys with sensitive data but seeks to adopt the latest international practices.
- **Archiving Policy:** TARKI's current policy only accepts fully anonymised databases, which may need adjustment for international data sharing.

Its next steps are to establish a TRE but TARKI requires help in setting up a Trusted Research Environment. The Driver can help here by establishing a strong framework as a roadmap for TARKI to follow.

⁶ <https://idan.network/>

⁷ <https://sshopencloud.eu/project>

At this stage, it is important to define what the Driver regards as a TRE, in order to establish how it can help in the process. In the view of Driver 2, a TRE is defined as a secure, monitored computing environment and controlled infrastructure that allows approved researchers to access sensitive/controlled data while ensuring data privacy and security is maintained. While legislation and frameworks differ across countries, common characteristics of TREs include:

- the existence of technical controls to ensure data security;
- access to the TRE is restricted to authorised researchers and projects;
- researchers can access data securely and perform analysis within the secure environment using the software available there;
- data cannot be downloaded from a TRE (though we recognise that other Drivers may have different arrangements for download/release of outputs);
- auditing and monitoring of users and usage takes place to protect data from unauthorised access; and
- measures are taken to ensure compliance with relevant data governance and privacy laws and standards.

Both UKDS and GESIS have existing TREs as part of their service in place:

- The UKDS TRE (UKDS SecureLab) and its security standard and philosophy are governed by the Five Safes Framework⁸. The UKDS SecureLab TRE conforms to the internationally-recognised information security management standard ISO 27001⁹, and is accredited for the sharing of controlled data under the UK Digital Economy Act (DEA)¹⁰. Data is not downloadable from SecureLab. Remote data access is possible from 1) an organisational desktop; 2) via the UKDA Safe Room; 3) via one of the Safe Pods across the UK and 4) internationally via the Safe Rooms of the IDAN partners IAB, CASD, and GESIS.
- The GESIS TRE is known as the GESIS Secure Data Center. The Five Safes Framework is being adopted for the Secure Data Center. Data is not downloadable, and data access is possible onsite via the Safe Rooms in Cologne and Mannheim, or remotely via the Safe Rooms of its IDAN partner UKDS.

TARKI does not currently have a TRE. Guidance and expertise from the Driver partners can help work towards the successful establishment of a TRE.

4.2.2 Users and user journey

UKDS, GESIS and TARKI agree as to who are our likely user groups:

⁸ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

⁹ <https://www.itgovernance.co.uk/iso27001-certification>

¹⁰

<https://uksa.statisticsauthority.gov.uk/digitaleconomyact-research-statistics/better-access-to-data-f-or-research-information-for-processors/>

- **Researchers** who wish to use the data;
- **Data custodians** who wish to share sensitive/detailed data, limiting access to trusted researchers, for specific projects, in a security-controlled, highly-monitored, specialist computing environment;
- **International infrastructure providers**, e.g. IDAN (for UKDS and GESIS) and additional international partners, such as TARKI, who wish to enable access to controlled data to users across countries.

The UKDS and GESIS TREs are both mature and have an established user journey, as described in Figure 4 for UKDS and Figure 5 for GESIS.

User journey UKDS SecureLab

- (1) ESRC Accredited Researcher Project Proposal or DEA Research Project Application
 (2) ESRC Accredited Researcher Status or DEA Accredited Researcher Status

Figure 4: The UKDS SecureLab user journey. EUL: End User License, DAC: Data Access Committee, SPE: Secure Processing Environment. In orange: user actions, in blue: TRE actions.

Figure 5: The GESIS TRE user journey. In orange: user actions, in blue: TRE actions, in green: steps in development.

4.2.3 Status

The Driver is assessing the framework materials created in the SSHOC project WP5.4¹¹¹² to underpin the cross-national sharing of secure data. For UKDS and GESIS, these materials are based on: a) their initial and successful use for secure data sharing via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access across TREs and countries in IDAN, including the setting up of contracts and liaising with data owners, and b) our experiences while setting up a connection between the TREs of GESIS and the UKDS within the SSHOC project. We are looking at potential test cases to test and strengthen the materials and blueprint for TRE collaborations with a new international partner. Key aims are to ensure the framework provides a pathway for TREs that are newly developing to follow, and to find new solutions to common problems.

TARKI does not yet have a TRE and so, as a key component of the driver work is ideally suited to help answer this question by working with the SSHOC framework materials to assess how useful they are in aiding completely new TREs and how they could be expanded or improved.

¹¹ Libby Bishop, Daan Broeder, Henk van den Heuvel, Brian Kleiner, Beate Lichtwardt, Deborah Wiltshire, & Yevhen Voronin. (2022). D5.10 White Paper on Remote Access to Sensitive Data in the Social Sciences and Humanities: 2021 and beyond (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6719121>.

¹² Beate Lichtwardt, Matthew Woollard, Deborah Wiltshire, & Elizabeth Lea Bishop. (2022). D5.11 ERAN Pilot: Setting up a Secure Remote Connection between two Trusted Research Environments (1,0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6676393>

4.2.4 Key capabilities

The SATRE framework contains three core pillars made up of capabilities that are considered important for TREs, plus a 4th pillar of supporting capabilities. Figure 6 outlines the capabilities that the UKDS and GESIS agree are important for their TREs and for this Driver.

Figure 6: SATRE Capabilities for the UKDS SecureLab and GESIS Secure Data Center

On first assessment, there were some differences between the capabilities highlighted by the UKDS and GESIS. For example, many of the supporting capabilities did not seem immediately relevant, for either UKDS or GESIS. There were a couple of reasons for this:

Firstly, the selected capabilities depend on the boundaries of the TREs. GESIS initially had a much narrower concept of their TRE than the UKDS, focusing primarily on the tasks and responsibilities under the remit of the Secure Data Center team. Supporting capabilities such as financial management and IT service management sit solely with teams outside of the Secure Data Center although their responsibilities impact on the TRE. To assess and agree on the required capabilities across the Driver, the scope extends beyond the immediate team to encompass all organisational groups whose tasks contribute to the effort.

Secondly, the legislative framework governing a TRE has an impact on what capabilities are important, and how readily a TRE meets the SATRE framework. The UKDS SecureLab is ISO27001 accredited and is also accredited under the Digital Economy Act (DEA). This is an important distinction as the DEA accreditation criteria are aligned with the SATRE framework by design. This means as an artefact of their accreditation, the UKDS SecureLab are required to show that they provide most of the SATRE capabilities. For other TREs, like the GESIS Secure Data Center, assessments against the SATRE framework must be newly conducted.

The sole capability not provided by either the UKDS or GESIS TRE is ‘Public involvement and engagement’ as these are not required at this time.

Key requirements most relevant to TREs in Driver 2 (as broadly classified in WP13):

1. Data transfer between environments:

- Data is not transferred out of the Organisation. For the UKDS SecureLab, data is not transferred out of the TRE itself, but at GESIS and TARKI data can also be stored in a secure location outside of the TRE but still under control of the organisation managing the TRE.
- Mandatory data encryption required during transit where applicable.
- Efficient data transfer protocols for handling large datasets will be needed in the future at GESIS for digital behavioural datasets.

2. User identity and access management:

- Verification of the user's identity before giving data access.
- Researcher ‘passport’ to enable cross-TRE authentication being investigated as a viable option (UK).

3. Governance and compliance:

- Development of governance models tailored to varying organisational and research needs.
- Compliance with domestic and international standards of data and information security management practices.
- Managing compliance with varied national legal frameworks for data sharing.

4. Data lifecycle management:

- Established mechanisms for the timely deletion of data post-expiration (UKDS), currently being established at GESIS.
- Secure integration and management of different sensitive data types, such as health records and questionnaires (UKDS).
- TARKI has not yet defined their requirements.

5. User training and certification:

- Ensure safe researcher training compliant with data access requirements.
- Creation and dissemination of general training modules focusing on curating and handling sensitive data across varied domains (established in the UK, currently under development in Germany).
- Standardisation of statistical disclosure control, such as output checker training and certification (established in the UK, currently under development in Germany).

In the Driver 2 workshop held on July 31, the UKDS, GESIS and TARKI assessed each of the requirements set out by all 4 Drivers, indicating which are mandatory or optional. Additional requirements were proposed by Driver 2, including multilingual metadata, findability, output release, citation and reproducibility and specialised ‘Safe Researcher’ training.

4.2.5 Uncertainties and next steps

As a next step, Driver 2 has agreed:

- TARKI will examine the SSHOC framework and work with UKDS and GESIS to identify potential legislative, technical and data landscape challenges that may prevent it sharing or providing access to controlled data of other TREs.
- Solutions to these challenges will be identified where possible.

For Driver 2, uncertainties lie in the following areas:

- Given the early stage of development of a TRE at TARKI, potential uncertainties might exist around resources for cooperation – i.e. whether there is sufficient physical space or qualified IT support.

4.3 Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe

4.3.1 Aim and scope

Driver 3 seeks to identify and overcome the data sharing challenges faced by the clinical research community. This will be achieved by: (i) exploring the use of TREs for the secure sharing and re-use of clinical trial data, and (ii) leveraging the untapped potential of routinely collected healthcare data within TREs to conduct robust clinical research.

Since 2016, prominent stakeholders—including medical journal editors¹³, the healthcare industry¹⁴, and research funders¹⁵—have advocated for the benefits of clinical trial data sharing and re-use. Despite this push, researchers still face significant challenges, such as uncertainty about ethical and legal requirements, selecting appropriate data sharing platforms, organising and structuring data for effective re-use, and concerns about misuse and scooping¹⁶. Currently, only 10-15% of clinical study Individual Participant Data (IPD) is shared, according to WHO's ICTRP Data Sharing Statements¹⁷.

¹³ Taichman DB, Sahni P, Pinborg A et al. Data Sharing Statements for Clinical Trials: A Requirement of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. *JAMA* (2017);317(24):2491-2492. doi: 10.1001/jama.2017.6514.

¹⁴ The PhRMA-EFPIA Principles for responsible clinical trial data sharing. <https://www.efpia.eu/media/qndlfduy/phrmaefpiaprinciplesforresponsibledatasharing2023.pdf>. Accessed on 09/08/2024

¹⁵ Kiley R, Peatfield T, Hansen J, Reddington F. Data Sharing from Clinical Trials - A Research Funder's Perspective. *N Engl J Med*. 2017;377(20):1990-1992. doi: 10.1056/NEJMs1708278

¹⁶ Stuart D, Baynes G, Hrynaszkiewicz I et al. (2018). Whitepaper: Practical challenges for researchers in data sharing (Version 1) [figshare]. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5975011.v1>

¹⁷ Merson L, Ndwandwe D, Malinga T et al. Promotion of data sharing needs more than an emergency: An analysis of trends across clinical trials registered on the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform. *Wellcome Open Res*. 2022;7:101. doi: 10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17700.1

Real World Data (RWD) refers to health-related data collected from a variety of sources outside of traditional clinical trials such as Electronic Health Records (EHR), medical claims and insurance data. Re-using RWD for research can have several applications¹⁸:

- Creating synthetic or external control groups and reducing the need for placebo groups.
- Facilitating clinical trial participant recruitment by assessing eligibility from EHRs.
- Enhancing the clinical trial dataset with RWD by feeding them directly into the clinical trial database (CDMS, eCapture). This could be applied for example to laboratory values.
- Conducting pragmatic trials and post-marketing surveillance. For example identifying rare adverse events and improving the generalisability of clinical trial results by including people from different cultural and ethnic backgrounds and with different comorbidities.

Clinical trial data are individual personal data used in research on the basis of informed consent. Routinely collected healthcare data are individual personal data used in research on the basis of public interest (usually). In both cases, the law requires that Technical and Organisational Measures (TOMs) are deployed to preserve the privacy and confidentiality of the data subjects. In this sense, TREs offer:

- *Security and Privacy*
- *Controlled Access*
- *Data Governance layer*
- *Auditing and Monitoring*
- *Collaboration and Sharing*: Maximising research investments¹⁹, enabling research de-duplication, contributing to overcoming the research reproducibility crisis, ensuring appropriate credit attribution
- *Public trust*: Transparency for patients and citizens

Additional services supporting clinical researchers can be proposed within TREs including:

- *Data de-identification / Data pseudonymisation / Data anonymisation*
- *Data standardisation*

4.3.2 Status

In Driver 3, two established TREs are engaged; the Sensitive Data Service (TSD)^{20, 21} of the University of Oslo, in Norway, which will be used for clinical trial data and the Health

¹⁸ Utilization of EHRs for clinical trials: a systematic review. BMC Med Res Methodol. 2024;24(1):70. doi: 10.1186/s12874-024-02177-7. PMID: 38494497

¹⁹ Glasziou P, Chalmers I. Research waste is still a scandal—an essay by Paul Glasziou and Iain Chalmers BMJ 2018; 363 :k4645 doi:10.1136/bmj.k4645

²⁰ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

²¹ [Documentation - TSD as a TRE](#)

Informatics Center (HIC)²² at the University of Dundee in Scotland, which provides services for the secure re-use of healthcare data. ECRIN²³ and HDR-UK²⁴ are crystallising requirements for the use of these TREs from the respective communities of clinical research and healthcare and through piloting with specific data sharing scenarios and stakeholder consultations. HDR-UK brings in also extensive experience in TRE federation from the DARE-UK initiative²⁵. Currently DARE-UK, including Driver 3 partners, is updating a Federated Architecture Blueprint²⁶ that will inform the requirements for the federation of clinical trials and healthcare TREs in the next phase of the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

Both the TREs of TSD and HIC are technologically mature and already provide services to researchers. For the use case of clinical trial data sharing there is still ongoing work as ECRIN and TSD collaborate to deliver a clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR)²⁷ that includes on top of the TRE an additional *governance layer, policies* and *supporting ELSI documentation* for data providers and re-users (such as contractual agreement templates, informed consent form template), *anonymisation guidelines* and *a metadata management system* for data FAIRification. The crDSR is currently being piloted within the BY-COVID project²⁸ for the data sharing of the VACCELERATE²⁹-funded clinical trial EU-COVAT-1 aged³⁰ that looked into the immunogenicity and reactogenicity of COVID-19 vaccination to elderly (≥75 years) adults.

4.3.3 Users and user journey

Broadly, two main profiles are expected to interact with TREs: data providers and data re-users. Data providers typically include *trial sponsors* and *principal investigators* from both academia and industry. For RWD, data providers are usually *healthcare professionals* and *public health institutes*. Data re-users are mainly *researchers* (clinical, academic, commercial, industry) including *data analysis professionals* (biostatisticians, data scientists). In more rare cases, data re-users can be *policy makers, patients* and *citizens*. In the case where data from a TRE are used to apply for marketing authorisation (e.g., of a medicinal product), TRE access from regulatory bodies (e.g., the European Medicines Agency-EMA) for auditing purposes would be required.

²² <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/hic>

²³ <https://ecrin.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>

²⁵ <https://dareuk.org.uk/>

²⁶ <https://dareuk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/DARE-UK-Federated-Architecture-1-Initial.pdf>

²⁷ <https://crdsr.ecrin.org/login>

²⁸ <https://by-covid.org/>

²⁹ <https://vaccelerate.eu/>

³⁰ Neuhann JM, Stemler J, Carcas AJ et al. Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of a first booster with BNT162b2 or full-dose mRNA-1273: A randomised VACCELERATE trial in adults ≥75 years (EU-COVAT-1). *Vaccine*. 2023 Nov 22;41(48):7166-7175. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2023.10.029. Epub 2023 Oct 31. PMID: 37919141.

Figure 7 depicts the *expected user journey for the re-use of a clinical trial dataset stored in a TRE*. The identification of the steps is based on the processes implemented by ECRIN and TSD in the context of the crDSR. Although these steps are generalisable enough to apply to most clinical trial data sharing scenarios that use a TRE³¹ specific requirements of data providers / TREs / data re-users often apply.

Figure 7: Expected user journey for re-users of clinical trial data in a TRE. In orange: journey steps requiring user actions. In blue: journey steps requiring TRE actions.

Figure 7 covers the scenario in which the re-user wants, for a specific research project, to access and analyse a clinical trial dataset that is already stored in a TRE. In reality, re-users such as meta-analysis specialists will need to access different clinical trial (or healthcare) datasets stored in different locations (*e.g., repositories using TREs, clinical trial sponsor local infrastructure*). Requirements for this type of federated use scenario will be collected and matured within Driver 3 over the following months.

The *expected user journey for the re-use of healthcare data in the TRE of the HIC* is depicted in Figure 8. HIC is applying the “Five Safes” principles (*Safe People* - authentication/logging of researchers, *Safe Projects* - ethical/governance approvals, *Safe Settings* - accredited environments/people, professional staff, verified processes (ISO27001), *Safe Data* - encryption, de-identification, minimised, *Safe Outputs* - statistical disclosure controls (incl. AI/ML). As a UK-based TRE, HIC is compliant with the SATRE mandatory criteria.

³¹ Pellen C, Le Louarn A, Spurrier-Bernard G et al. Ten (not so) simple rules for clinical trial data-sharing. PLoS Comput Biol. 2023;19(3):e1010879. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010879.

Figure 8: Expected user journey for re-users of a healthcare dataset within the TRE of HIC. AI: Artificial Intelligence, ML: Machine Learning

4.3.4 Key capabilities

The Driver 3 requirements for TREs were principally collected during an internal EOSC-ENTRUST workshop that took place on the 23rd of July 2024 and included representatives from all Driver 3 partners: ECRIN, UiO, University of Dundee, HDR-UK. The WP7 leads and Drivers 1, 2 and 4 were also invited to attend.

Overall, the partners reached consensus that the SATRE specification³² effectively captures the Driver 3 needs. Taking into account the “user perspective” (for both the roles of *data provider* and *data re-user*) a TRE needs to offer **Information Governance, Computing Technology, Data Management** and **Supporting Capabilities** (see Figure 9).

³² <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

Figure 9: Key capabilities from the SATRE framework for Driver 3

The Driver 3 partners also reviewed the list of requirements (.csv file published with this report) and evaluated each identified requirement as “*Must-have*”, “*Should-have*”, “*Could-have*”, “*Won’t-have*” and “*Non applicable*”.

Specific capabilities identified as important by the Driver 3 partners:

- **Contractual agreements:** A TRE must have legal services that cover “contractual agreements” with the users (both *data providers* and *data re-users* in the case of Driver 3).
- **Certification:** Demonstrating good information management and security via certifications such as “*ISO/IEC 27001 - Information Security Management*” and “*ISO/IEC 27701 - Privacy Information Management*” is definitely useful to convince data providers (=data controllers) that their legal obligation of safeguarding sensitive data security and confidentiality is covered but it is not a “must-have” for TREs.
- **Data Encryption:** All data within the Trusted Research Environment must be encrypted *in transit*. This requirement aims to ensure that data is protected from unauthorised access or breaches. On the contrary, data encryption *at rest* is not seen as a necessary requirement for TREs (as evaluated by the Driver 3 partners).
- **Software applications:** Data re-users should have access to appropriate and familiar analysis software within the TRE project space. Ideally, a TRE should also allow researchers to 'bring their own software' to facilitate cutting-edge research, including applications of machine learning and artificial intelligence.
- **Archiving for future validation or reproducibility under regulations:** Certain datasets, especially those used in clinical research for regulatory submissions, must be preserved long-term. This may also involve archiving the specific analysis environment, including code, scripts, and intermediate results. Consequently, formal

digital archiving processes and curation actions may be required. TREs supporting clinical trials must be equipped with this capability.

- **Basic training on the use of the TRE's project space:** Potential users are not necessarily familiar with working in a TRE. Driver 3 partners have specifically consulted meta-analysis experts who claim that so far their *modus operandi* has been sensitive data file downloads and analysis in their own machines. As such, basic user guidelines or guidance videos or ad-hoc training could be an option to increase user friendliness and user satisfaction.
- **Data kept only within the agreed time period:** TREs must implement mechanisms for timely deletion of the data (e.g., from users' project space when this exceeds the authorised period or completely from the TRE when this goes beyond the data provider's requirements).
- **Credit attribution to the original data generator:** Often publications coming out by research provided by others require a review process by the original data provider's team. Often also credit attribution is required (e.g., co-authorship / acknowledgement in publications). TREs can play a key role in incentivising sensitive data sharing by providing credit attribution policies and mechanisms.
- **Dataset discovery:** TREs may employ discovery mechanisms that include automated processes for identifying suitable datasets for a research project or clinical trial. These might be federated to allow for multi-TRE querying (e.g., HDR Cohort Discovery Tool³³).
- **Metadata:** Appropriate metadata³⁴ to allow for data object findability and re-usability should be in place.
- **Data standardisation/data anonymisation:** Support with data standardisation and data anonymisation is provided in the context of some TREs (e.g., some healthcare TREs map all their datasets in OMOP, some clinical trial TREs have CDISC conversion services). Although this is often not seen as a capability that the TREs should provide, in practice data providers and data re-users would greatly benefit from such additional support.

4.3.5 Uncertainties and next steps

Driver 3 has provided baseline requirements and key capabilities from the users' perspective (e.g., clinical trial sponsors, healthcare providers, public health institutes, researchers, data analysts), but the feasibility of covering these within the “boundaries of the TRE” needs to be assessed within the TRE Providers Forum and reflected in first draft of the EOSC-ENTRUST architecture blueprint. Driver 3 partners concluded that a layered approach as the one presented in the Federated Architecture Blueprint of DARE-UK³⁵

³³ <https://www.healthdatagateway.org/about/cohort-discovery>

³⁴ <https://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/forthcoming.php?icode=ijmso>

³⁵ <https://dareuk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/DARE-UK-Federated-Architecture-1-Initial.pdf>

seems to be an appropriate model. The DARE-UK blueprint foresees: i) an “infrastructure layer”, ii) a “data layer” and iii) “a governance layer”.

In the following months, we expect that the lessons learned from the piloting scenarios (e.g., data sharing from EU-COVAT-1-AGED trial) together with stakeholder consultations (e.g., via surveys, workshops) and desktop search will lead to the refinement of the identified baseline requirements. In addition, a concrete scenario involving both clinical trial data and routinely collected healthcare data is still to be elaborated by the Driver 3 partners as the model that will set interoperability requirements across the domains of clinical trials and routine healthcare.

4.4 Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data

4.4.1 Aim and scope

Driver 4 focuses on collaborative data processing between higher education and research institutions and their private sector partners. The key problems it addresses include secure data collaboration, optimal data management, lack of protocols and digital solutions, efficient collaboration, and proof-of-concept evaluation. By leveraging a TRE, Driver 4 ensures that sensitive data can be jointly analysed while adhering to privacy regulations. It also allows customisation to meet national needs and provides a controlled space for testing and refining data processing workflows. Ultimately, the goal is to facilitate effective research collaboration while safeguarding data integrity and security.

Driver 4 has three partners: Turku University of Applied Sciences (TUAS), CSC, and Sigma2. At this stage, the focus of the Driver 4 is on the SD (sensitive data) services provided for academic research use by CSC. SD services are designed to support secure sensitive data management through web-user interfaces accessible from the user's own computer. SD services are composed of four components including SD Connect (store and share), SD Desktop (compute), SD Submit (data submission), and SD Apply (access management) that together help users manage sensitive data during all the phases of a research project.

4.4.2 Users and user journey

We have identified three types of organisations which are relevant for public–private interaction in research and innovation projects: research institutions, private organisations and public organisations. Users of TRE could represent any of these organisations and the main roles include principal investigator, researcher, and data provider (see Table 1).

Table 1: Users in Driver 4

Type of organisation	User roles
----------------------	------------

Research institution	Principal investigator, researcher, data manager
Private organisation	Data provider, co-researcher, developer, data manager
Public organisation	Data provider, co-researcher, developer, data manager

Essential part of using SD service is access to the services. Hence, workflows were created from the viewpoint of two essential user roles: principal investigator and researcher. Their workflow to access SD services is demonstrated in Figure 10 and 11.

Figure 10: Principal investigator’s workflow for SD services

Figure 11: Research’s workflow for SD services

4.4.3 Status

TUAS has been actively using multiple TREs, some offered by CSC and others by different parties. These include SD services which have been trialed in a few research projects. Additionally, TUAS has been actively working on research projects in the realm of synthetic data generation and federated learning using other TREs (e.g. Auria Biobank).

In the context of Driver 4, TUAS has not yet been able to use SD services due constraints in the current phase in application development. Expanding the usage of SD services to company partners would require changes in CSC's Terms of Use.³⁶

4.4.4 Key capabilities

For Driver 4, the following SATRE capabilities were most appropriate:

- End user computing
- Output management
- Governance Requirements
- Information security

In addition, Driver 4 identified the following capabilities that are missing from the SATRE framework:

- **Service design:** Service design is needed to create easy access to services of the TRE for end-users in different roles. Also the workflow required to share and analyse data should be made as easy as possible.
- **Ethical guidance:** TRE should assure that users understand their ethical responsibilities while analysing sensitive data. The guidance could be offered by the TRE. It is also possible for the TRE to require organisations that use their services to offer such guidance for the users from their organisation.
- **Backup:** The TRE should create a backup copy of the data analyses for the full length of research project.

4.4.5 Uncertainties and next steps

To test the usage of SD services in the selected cases for Driver 4, synthetic data could be used for piloting the service usability, analysis tools and computing power. Currently, Driver 4 has focused on use cases in the health technologies thus analysing sensitive data related to people's health and wellbeing. However, it might be of interest to include new cases to better understand requirements for TREs which are related to public-private interaction on environmental data. These cases could include research and innovation projects between research institutions and private companies in the field of maritime studies.

5. Results & Discussion

5.1 Results Driver workshops

This section summarises the results of the Driver's requirements gathering process and provides an across-drivers analysis. The results reported here and in Chapter 4 have been

³⁶ <https://research.csc.fi/general-terms-of-use>

gathered in a series of workshops as well as offline. A comprehensive version of the across-drivers analysis reported in this section can be found in “MS7_SATRE capabilities mapping” and “MS7_User journeys mapping” .csv files published with this report.

Users

All drivers reported their existing and/or expected users in Chapter 4. An analysis over the four drivers revealed that the categories of *data users* and *data providers* constitute distinct and important users for all of the drivers. The aim and use cases of the drivers then determine which user profiles can be found within those categories (see Table 2), where *researchers* are the most common data users for all of the drivers.

Infrastructure providers are reported as users by drivers 1 and 2, while *regulatory bodies* are only reported by Drivers 1 and 3. The question of who are considered users of a TRE has been extensively discussed in the workshops, where *infrastructure providers* and *regulatory bodies* are considered stakeholders, but not actual users of the TRE by some of the Drivers. These stakeholders might need access to the TRE under specific circumstances, for example for audits in the case of *regulatory bodies* and to provide technical support in the case of *infrastructure providers*. Further discussion is needed to arrive at a common definition of *users* versus *stakeholders*, since this definition influences the scope of TRE requirements.

Table 2: Mapping of user categories and users between the four Drivers

User category	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4
Data users	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers, policy makers, patients and citizens	Principal investigator, researcher, co-researcher, developer
Data providers	Data Custodians/Submitters	Data Custodians	trial sponsors, principal investigators, healthcare professionals, public health institutes	Principal investigator, Data provider, data manager
Infrastructure Providers	Infrastructure Providers	International infrastructure Providers		
Regulatory Bodies	Regulatory Bodies		Regulatory Bodies (e.g., the EMA, FDA, MHRA)	

User journey

The user journeys reported in Chapter 4 by the four Drivers have been mapped to each other, based on the template user journey provided to each of the Drivers as an example (Table 3). From this mapping, an overarching user journey emerges where individual Drivers or TREs might or might not include all steps. An analysis of which Drivers/TREs report which steps can be found in Table 3, with a full description of all steps per Driver/TRE included in on the *User journeys* tab. It should be noted that the user journey for CSC SD Services might include more steps that were not reported.

Table 3: Mapping of user journeys between the four Drivers. For Driver 2, both the user journeys for UKDS SecureLab and GESIS have been included, since these were reported separately and differ in some steps.

Generic steps	Driver 1	Driver 2: UKDS SecureLab	Driver 2: GESIS	Driver 3: clinical trial and healthcare	Driver 4
Registration		x		x	x
TRE user agreement		x		Data Use Agreement including TRE-related clauses or TRE User Agreement	x
Data discovery	x		x	x	
Feasibility assessment	x		x		
Data request	x	x	x	x	
Evaluation of request	x	x	x	x	
Safe researcher training		x	x	x	
Data use agreement	x	x	x	x	
Project space preparation	x	x	x	x	x
Software installation	x		x	x	
Data move to hot storage	x				
User authorization	x	x	x	x	x
User access	x	x	x	x	x
User DIY software installation	x			x	
Analysis	x	x	x	x	
Import request		x	x		
Export request	x	x	x	x	
Export of results	x	x	x	x	
Publication	x	x	x	x	

Key SATRE capabilities

All Drivers identified the key capabilities from the SATRE framework that are important to the Driver. The key capabilities are reported in detail in Chapter 4 and an overview for all drivers can be found in [M7.1 - Drivers mapping](#) on the *SATRE capabilities mapping* tab. The capabilities “*End user computing*”, “*Information security*” and “*governance requirements*” were reported as key capabilities for all drivers. Moreover, *Public involvement and engagement* was placed out of scope for all Drivers and was not reported as a capability of any of the TREs involved in the Drivers.

Table 4 summarises the capabilities that were reported as important for the drivers, but missing from the SATRE framework. The ability to include capabilities and requirements that go beyond the SATRE framework will be important when designing a requirements management framework for EOSC-ENTRUST.

Table 4: Key capabilities reported as missing from the SATRE framework by the Drivers

Missing Capabilities	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4
Anonymization	x		x	
Internet Connection from within TRE	x			
Scalable Infrastructure	x			
data standardisation/ common data models			x	
Data transfer between environments		x		
Service design				x
Ethical guidance			x	x
Backup				x

5.2 Requirements management framework

From the work reported by the Drivers in Chapter 4 we can derive that there is great variability between the Drivers with regard to the scope and aims for TREs, resulting in different requirements. In addition, data users and data providers play different roles in the driver projects and therefore in the TREs that may or may not be used in these projects, which in turn results in different requirements for TREs. It is important for EOSC-ENTRUST to consider each of these perspectives when gathering requirements.

The Providers Forum has been tasked with establishing a requirements management framework for EOSC-ENTRUST. This requirements management framework can support harmonisation between the requirements gathered by the four drivers, taking the data users’ and data providers’ perspective into account. Moreover, a common framework provides a means to map driver requirements on provider capabilities to inform the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and can be used beyond the EOSC-ENTRUST project. The Providers Forum has taken a first step by bringing together the Architecture, Drivers and

Providers work packages to discuss such a common requirements management framework. However, to arrive at a framework that can support all three WPs and can be used beyond the EOSC-ENTRUST project more alignment between the Work Packages is needed. Since this was not attainable within the timeline for the current milestone report, requirements from the Drivers were gathered in a common spreadsheet, where mappings were added to show fit-gap between Drivers and with the SATRE framework:

- MoSCoW mappings for each Driver on each requirement
- A mapping of each requirement to a SATRE capability

As soon as a common requirements management framework becomes available within EOSC-ENTRUST, the list of requirements will be updated to match that framework.

5.2 Driver requirements

Driver requirements have been gathered through different means: the first Requirements and Capabilities Workshop, held on May 7-8, 2024 by the Architecture Work Package (WP13) and reported in D13.1, the [Draft Roadmap for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint](#), the Drivers baseline requirements workshop followed by the focus workshops for each Driver (see section 5.1 for workshop results) and through internal Driver meetings and offline gathering of requirements. The requirements gathered for the four Drivers have been compiled in a single spreadsheet. The v1.0 version of the Drivers' list of requirements is published in .csv format with this report. The Drivers' list of requirements is a living document that will be updated throughout the project, with later versions being released with the year 2 and year 3 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers (M8 and M9).

5.3 Trends and issues

From the requirements gathering process, it becomes clear that the Drivers are in different stages regarding identifying what is needed for the use cases they serve. All drivers use at least one mature TRE (see Table 5), some of the drivers use a TRE that is under development and some of the drivers are just starting to develop or use a TRE. The use cases that drivers bring to the table will play an important role in (further) developing the TREs.

Table 5: Maturity of TREs used by partners within the Drivers

Status TRE	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4
Mature TRE	SD-Services	UKDS SecureLab, GESIS	TSD, HIC	SD-Services
TRE under development	BSC/CRG			
No TRE in use		TARKI		

A second observation is that the scope or definition of a TRE differs between the drivers and between the partners involved in the drivers. Two more prominent differences are: 1) to what extent are governance and data life cycle in scope for TREs and 2) whether TREs are used for temporary, project-based data analysis, or long term storage of data collections (or something in between). For the purpose of gathering requirements relevant to all Drivers and partners, we will keep a broad scope where each of the Drivers can decide what applies to them when defining requirements.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the European Health Data Space (EHDS) will introduce a new legal framework, which includes specific requirements for SPEs (as TREs tend to be called in the context of the EHDS).

A pitfall for some of the Drivers is that they tend to focus on the capabilities of existing TRE solutions. This interferes with taking the user's perspective when gathering requirements, which is the key role of the Drivers for gathering input for the Blueprint. Capabilities and solutions implemented by different TRE providers are already gathered by the Provider Forum. It is therefore essential for the Drivers to take the perspective of the users when further gathering and refining requirements, where both data users and data providers should be taken into account and conflation of the roles of data providers with TRE providers should be avoided.

6. Conclusions

The four Drivers have defined their *Problem*, their *Users*, their *User Journey* for as far as possible in this stage of the project and all drivers have gathered the *Requirements* most relevant to them. In Figure 12, a visual overview is given of the status of each of the drivers relative to the aims for year 1 (WP7).

Figure 12: Visual overview of roadmap towards end of year and the status of the drivers relative to this roadmap (arrows)

To further align with the goals of the Drivers WP, namely informing and validating the Blueprint and providing user input to the Providers Forum, the current results point to two important takeaways:

- Put the user first when gathering requirements from the Driver perspective, use a design thinking approach

- Take the needs of both data users and data providers in TREs into account, since these lead to different requirements

7. Next steps

The current milestone report will serve as a basis to provide input to the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint during the Evaluation & Adoption workshop organised in September 2024 by the Architecture WP (WP13). In preparation for this, the Drivers WP will align the results reported here with the needs of WP13.

In addition to the Evaluation & Adoption workshop, the Drivers are considering the organisation of an in-person Drivers workshop towards the end of the year. Aims for this workshop could be:

- a. Defining aims and a detailed roadmap for year 2
- b. Defining a common requirements gathering framework together with the Provider Forum and the Architecture WP
- c. Gathering requirements among a larger group of (current and future) TRE users using a design thinking approach

In addition to the workshops, Drivers 1, 3 and 4 propose to design surveys, where the scope differs based on the aims of the Drivers:

- Driver 1 aims to gather specific data-owners requirements, subsequently to be mapped to the SATRE framework
- Driver 3 aims to gather specific requirements from clinical trial sponsors and PIs on requirements for data sharing, including via the use of TREs
- Driver 4 aims to gather requirements from (potential) data users

The surveys will be shared among the Drivers and will align with the survey³⁷ already sent out before by the Providers Forum.

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/12623607>

Appendix 1: Abbreviations

IDAN	International Data Access Network
crDSR	clinical research Data Sharing Repository
DAA	Data Access Agreement
DEA	UK Digital Economy Act
ICTRP	International Clinical Trials Registry Platform
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications
GDI	Genomics Data Infrastructure
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPD	Individual Participant Data
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
RWD	Real World Data
SATRE	Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
TOM	Technical and Organisational Measure
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

Appendix 2: Overview of drivers and partners

Driver	Partners
Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision	CSC CRG BSC
Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data	CESSDA GESIS UKDS TARKI
Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe	ECRIN UiO HDR UK UNIVDUN
Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data	Turku UAS CSC Sigma2